

STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC FEATURES OF OLD ENGLISH ANTHROPONYMS

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Abstract: This article discusses the brief history of Old English naming process. Different stages in English anthroponomy, ways of formation of personal names and underlying factors in name giving process have been analyzed with relevant examples as well.

Key words: Anthroponomicon in onomastics, Old English personal names, anthroponymy, anthroponimic unit.

Anthroponymy as a section of onomastics that studies the naming of a person (anthroponyms), not only studies the structure, etymology, semantics of the name, but also the reflection in the name of the qualities of a person, his connections with clan and family, class, caste, ethnos, place of birth [3, P.26]. In addition, anthroponymics studies the functions of an anthroponym in speech, such as the function of nomination, differentiation, identification, change of name related to age, change in social or marital status, temporary (short or long) migration, change of citizenship, entry into secret societies, adoption of another religion, etc.

The proper name contains cultural information that reflects the ethnic and aesthetic attitudes of society. The name is associated with various periods of social and cultural life, each of which is characterized by stereotypical ideas about the function of the name and reflects the events of the spiritual and political life of society.

All proper names, including anthroponyms, carry cultural, historical and social significance. Naming a child by a name is a linguistic creative activity that

takes into account psychological, social and cultural factors. The personal name serves as a kind of concentration of the culture of the people, and at the same time it itself is a product of the national culture.

Anthroponyms are understood as one of the classes of proper names, words and phrases “officially assigned to an individual as his identification mark” [1, P. 38]. They represent various naming conventions of a person, such as first names, surnames, pseudonyms, nicknames.

Anthroponymicon is a universal lexical component of any language. It has a rich set of names for the individual. Each nation has its own anthroponymicon, its own calendar, lists, register of personal names.

An anthroponymicon is understood as: 1) a dictionary or list of anthroponyms, usually compiled separately for personal names (and patronymics from them), for surnames, for nicknames, for old non-canonical names, and 2) the repertoire of the names of a given people or society in a certain period. The same as the nameplate [4, P.33].

Any anthroponymic unit is a product of socio-historical development, created at a certain period of history and passed down from generation to generation. An enlarged, polished, multi-variant unit reaches our days. Consideration of this process, its systematic analysis based on scientifically grounded facts helps to clarify some key and contradictory moments in the development of language, the history of a particular ethnic group [6, P.22]. There are many factors influencing the choice of a person's name. They were presented in a systematized form by O.A. Leonovich, who distinguishes among them such as the influence of fashion, the connection of a name with a certain social group, the desire to avoid difficult combinations, the influence of religion, the desire to be branded as original, the influences of associations with historical or cultural figures, the desire to capture memory about relatives [2, P.15].

The nomenclature of modern English personal names is very diverse: it includes ancient and new names, native English and borrowed ones, traditional and invented, differing from each other in structural and semantic features.

English personal names have come a long way of historical development, reflecting changes in the history of the English people and the English language.

Among the English anthroponyms, it is customary to distinguish:

1. Old English personal names,
2. Middle English anthroponymicon,
3. New English Anthroponymicon,
4. Modern anthroponymicon [5, P.15].

In Old English anthroponymics, only personal names existed, which in structure could be simple (Froda - poet.wise; old; Hwita - white, light, shiny, etc.) and complex (Eadgar - poet.property, possession, property: happiness; rich + poet spear, etc.).

After the XIII century. simple names have been completely supplanted by complex, two-part names. The components of complex names were drawn from a special collection of Old English nominal words. The Anglo-Saxons believed in the magical properties of “benevolent” nominal words to give the bearer of the name protection and patronage, wealth, health, prosperity, courage, glory, honor. These include the following Old English words: beorn - man, warrior, hero; beorht - bright, shiny, light aelf - elf; eald - old, old, old; god - good, good, gift; gifu, gyfu - gift, gift; maere - famous, glorious; rice - powerful, high rank, rich; raed -advice, solution; sae - sea, lake; stan - stone; sunu - son; weard - guard, protection, patronage, keeper; wig - struggle, war, valor, military strength; wine - friend; wulf - wolf, etc. Some of these words apparently had a strictly defined place in a complex name, that is, they could be either only the first or only the second component of the name, and part of the nominal words could be occupied by either of these two places. [2, P.39].

In the following table three different positions of components of complex names have been illustrated:

Fisrt components			Second components			Any components		
Component	Meaning	Example	Component	Meaning	Example	Component	Meaning	Example
Eald	old	Ealdwine	-read	Advice solution	Hilread	Beorth	bright shiny	Cudbeorth
Aelf	elf	Aelfstan	-gifu	Gift	Aelfgifu	Maere	famous	Adelmaere
God	good	Godwine	-ric	Rich powerful	Cedric	Wine	friend	Godwine
			-stan	Stone	Adelstan	Wig	struggle wine	Eadwig
			-weard	Guard	Aelfweard	Wulf	wolf	Beowulf

Table 1. Components of Old English complex names.

In terms of structural and semantic features, Old English female names did not differ from male names. The second component was an indicator of the gender of the name. In male names, it was represented by masculine nouns: gar - spear, dart; helm - helmet; hafoc - hawk; here - army, army; man - person, raed - advice, decision, reason, means; stan; sunu; wig; weard; wine: Eadgar, Ælfstan, Hildræd / Hilred. The second component of feminine names, respectively, were feminine nouns: burg, burn - dwelling behind the wall, fortress, castle; gyfu, gifu - gift, gift; frithu - the world; hen - chicken; guth - battle, war; run - secret, secret, secret advice: Eadburg, Ælfgifu. Adjectives were also used as second components. In male names, these were adjectives that determined the social status and character traits of the bearer of the name: beald - bold, self-confident, cool; heah - high; beorht - bright, shiny, light ric - powerful, high rank, rich; heard - hard: Eadberht, Cenric, Heard.

Among female names, the second component was the adjective swiþ - strong: Ælfswiþ, Friðuswiþ / Frideswide.

A major political event that influenced the further development of the English people and the English language, as you know, is the invasion of England by the Normans. The conquerors imported their anthroponyms (Hugo, Ralph, Richard, Rodger, William, etc.), which soon began to supplant the Anglo-Saxon names. The assimilation of new names went on more intensively among the ruling circles. Only a few Anglo-Saxon names survived, for example, Alfred, Edgar, Edward, Hilda, Mildred, etc.

In the Middle Ages, Old English names disappeared from the English anthroponymicon and, in connection with the strengthening of the power of the church, biblical names became widespread (Adam, Sarah, Eve, Sampson, Joseph, Daniel, David, Susanna, Anna (from the Old Testament), Peter, Baptist, John, James, Matthew, Simon, Thomas (from the New Testament)). By law, it was allowed to name the child by any name of the godparents' choice.

To summarise, it is noteworthy to mention that English naming process have witnessed various changes over different periods. This process can be seen in other nations' language as well. Any anthroponymic unit is a product of socio-historical development, created at a certain period of history and passed down from generation to generation. An enlarged, polished, multi-variant unit reaches our days. Consideration of this process, its systematic analysis based on scientifically grounded facts helps to clarify some key and contradictory moments in the development of language, the history of a particular ethnic group.

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